

UTILISATION OF NEYVELI CLAYS. PART I. PRELIMINARY STUDIES ON ADSORPTIVE PROPERTIES

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White clay of particle size (-200+270 mesh) from Neyveli lignite field, kaolinitic in character, has been activated by treatment with hydrochloric acid. The adsorptive properties of unactivated raw clay of the same particle size and the activated clay have been studied in comparison with the I.C.I. Earth "Fulmont 525C". Raw vegetable oils of different colour intensities and different pigment natures and varied viscosities have been subjected to treatment by the earths and the results analysed by applying the Freundlich adsorption isotherm equation to the data obtained. The laboratory-activated clay is found to have comparatively high apparent activity.

The discovery of the lignite deposits in South Arcot district has opened up immense possibilities for the industrialisation of this part of the country. Besides lignite being important as a fuel, the important over-burden of clay deposits requires attention regarding proper utilisation. The samples from the clay bed at different depths over the lignite have been analysed. The analysis has shown that the clay is essentially kaolinitic in character¹ and the bulk of it lacks sufficient plasticity to be capable of being used up as such in ceramic industries. It has, however, been adjudged useful as a refractory material.

India is poor in its resources of naturally active adsorbent materials of the type of Fuller's earth, and hence, large quantities of Fuller's earth and activated earths are imported into India to meet the requirements of the Vanaspati and other industries². The starting of the petroleum oil refineries further increases the demand for activated clays. As the clay deposits are almost inexhaustible, and South Arcot district is also a big centre of production of groundnut and other oil seeds, a study of the adsorptive properties of Neyveli clay with reference to raw vegetable oils in the first instance has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

The sample of clay received from the Lignite Investigation Officer, Neyveli, has the following characteristics :

TABLE I

Tests on clay as received³.

1. Volatile content (loss on heating at 188°F for ten minutes)	...	0.64%
2. Moisture content (loss at 220°F)	...	0.69%
3. Vol. wt. of clay or bulk density	...	57.8 lb./cu. ft.
4. Screen analysis	...	15% passing through 200 mesh
5. Acidity	...	Neutral.

As it is reported that a clay having a fraction of 90 to 95% (least 50%) passing through 200 mesh is used for refining vegetable oils⁴, the clay was wet ground initially in a Pascalf Ball mill, filtered, dried and reground (dry) in the ball mill. The ground material was then sieved and the material passing through 200 mesh screen (U. S. Standard sieves) and retained on 270 mesh was used for bleaching experiments. The bulk density of this material was 48.96 lbs. per cubic foot.

Activation of the clay.—White clay, ground and sieved, as described before, was mixed with 10% Be HCl in the proportion 25 g : 50 c.c. respectively and refluxed with an air condenser for 3 hours. The clay was filtered, washed free of acid and dried at 110°. The dried product was reheated to 400° and maintained at that temperature for 3 hours, cooled and stored over a desiccant.

Bleaching and measurement of colour.—Previously dried and filtered vegetable oil (100 g.) was heated over a steam bath to the required temperature and stirred vigorously with the aid of a paddle type stirrer attached to a vari-speed motor. The stirrer was so adjusted that it was near the bottom of the vessel. The pre-determined quantity of the adsorbent was then added and kept agitated for a period of 15 minutes, at the end of which the oil was filtered through a hot fluted filter. The colour of the treated oil was then measured in a Klett-Summerson photo-electric colorimeter using the light filter No. 54 (supplied with the instrument corresponding to the approximate spectral range 500—570 m μ) and 20 mm. cells, as also in a Lovibond tintometer.

The results of the experiments of treating Hongey oil (*Pongamia glabra*) with unactivated raw clay and activated clay are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Dried, filtered Hongey oil of colour 27Y and 4.1 R in 2" cell. Temp. = 90°-95°.

Adsorbent.	Conc.	Lovibond colour of treated oil.	Remarks.
Unact. raw clay	1%	27Y 5.0R	} No bleaching. Colour intensifies
	5	27Y 5.4R	
Act. clay	1	27Y 5.0R	
	5	27Y 5.5R	

In Table III are tabulated the results obtained with Castor oil and laboratory-activated clay, unactivated raw clay and Fulmont 525C. Data for evaluation of constants k and n in the Freundlich adsorption isotherm ($\log x/m = \log k + n \log C$) are also given.

TABLE III
Oil treated : 100 g. raw castor oil of colour 170.[#]
Temp. = 80°—90°.

% Adsorbent. (m)	Colour of treated oil. (C)	Colour* removed. (x)	% Bleach. (x/m).	log. x/m.	log C.	n (calc.)	(-log k).
Adsorbent : Activated clay							
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	9.
1	131	39	22.9	39.0	1.59	2.12	4.67
3	102	68	40.0	22.7	1.36	2.01	4.70
5	99	71	41.8	14.2	1.15	1.99	4.76
7	87	83	48.8	11.9	1.07	1.94	4.66
9	83	87	51.2	9.7	0.99	1.92	4.69
						Av. 2.96	4.69
							$k=2.0 \times 10^{-4}$
Adsorbent : Unactivated raw clay.							
1	150	20	11.7	20	1.30	2.18	2.17
3	125	45	26.5	15	1.18	2.09	2.17
5	110	60	35.3	12	1.03	2.04	2.17
7	94	76	44.7	11	1.04	1.97	2.11†
9	90	80	47.1	9	0.95	1.95	2.16
						Av. 1.59	2.16
							$k=6.74 \times 10^{-3}$
Adsorbent : I. C. I. Earth Fulmont 525C.							
1	134	36	21.2	36.0	1.56	2.13	8.91
3	114	56	32.9	18.7	1.27	2.06	8.86*
5	105	65	38.2	13.0	1.11	2.02	8.87
7	107	63	37.1	9.0	0.95	2.03	9.04
9	102	68	40.0	7.5	0.87	2.01	8.98
						Av. 4.92	8.93
							$k=11.7 \times 10^{-10}$

The scale of the photoelectric colorimeter is logarithmic and the concentration of the colouring matter is directly proportional to the scale reading as given here.

The results of experiments with *Til* oil are shown in Table IV. The conditions are the same as in Castor oil.

TABLE IV*

Adsorbent : Activated clay.					Adsorbent : Unactivated raw clay.				Adsorbent : I. C. I. Earth Fulmont 525C.			
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	2.	3.	4.	5.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1	210	16	7.1	16.0	224	2	0.9	2.0	220	6	2.65	6.0
3	193	33	14.6	11.0	214	12	5.3	4.0	214	12	5.3	4.0
5	174	52	23.0	10.4	208	18	8.0	3.6	207	19 ^c	8.4	3.8
7	157	69	30.5	10.0	196	30	13.3	4.3	194	32	14.2	4.6
n (calc.)=4.32. Av.=2.0					$k=2.76 \times 10^{-4}$.				n (calc.)=14.7			

Column headings in this and subsequent tables are as in Table III.

Raw groundnut oil, dried and filtered, having 'Colour 40' was treated at 75° to 85° as in other experiments. The results of experiments are reported in Tables V, VI and VII.

TABLE V

Adsorbent : Activated clay.

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	(log k) 9.
1	31	9	22.5	9.0	0.95	1.49		0.17
3	18	22	55.0	7.0	0.84	1.25	0.46	0.19
5	13	27	67.5	5.4	0.73	1.11	0.59	0.15
							Av. 0.52	0.17
								$k=0.68$

TABLE VI

Adsorbent : Unactivated raw clay.

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1	38	2	5	2.0
3	37	3	7.5	1.0
5	31	9	22.5	1.8
7	25	15	37.5	2.1
9	20.5	19.5	48.7	2.2

TABLE VII

Adsorbent : I. C. I. Earth Fulmont 525C.

1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1	35	5	12.5	5.0
3	30	10	25.0	3.3
5	30	10	25.0	2.0
7	24.5	15.5	38.7	2.2
9	21	19	47.7	2.1

n (calc.)=27.

DISCUSSION

A study of the data in Table III shows that the relation between the adsorption of the colouring matter in raw castor oil and the equilibrium concentration of the colouring matter in the oil can fairly be expressed by the Freundlich equation, $x/m = k.C^n$ in all the cases studied ; k is a measure of the decolorising power of the adsorbent and n indicates the characteristics of adsorption. A good adsorbent should normally have a high value of k . A high value of n shows that the adsorbent will remove first portions

of colour only and is not effective in bleaching to a high degree. The high value of 4.92 for n in the case of Fulmont 525C, when compared with the low value for Neyveli Earths, shows that it is effective in removing the first portions of colour from the oil but thereafter the activity is very limited, and hence, cannot be used to effect a very high degree of decolorisation⁵. Of the three adsorbents studied, the activated Neyveli clay is fairly effective over the range of concentration of the adsorbent tried in these experiments, but the unactivated clay would be active over a wider range.

The data with respect to treatment of raw *Til* oil (cf. Table IV) show that the application of the Freundlich equation is very limited. The value of x/m after an initial comparatively appreciable reduction tends towards a constant value with the activated clay, Fulmont 525C. There is no initial reduction in value in the case of unactivated clay. Of the three adsorbents, the activated clay has a greater 'apparent activity'. The same characteristic way of adsorption is observed in the case of treatment of raw groundnut oil also.

It is seen from this comparative study that under the same conditions of temperature and contact time, the characteristics of adsorption depend upon the nature of the oil; for oils of about the same density, viscosity of the oil markedly affects the nature of adsorption (cf. data for castor oil and other oils). For oils of similar density and viscosity under identical conditions of experiment, the adsorption characteristics are the same irrespective of the initial colour of the oil.

That adsorption depends upon the nature of the pigment in the oil is borne out by the failure of the Neyveli clays to remove colour from Hongey oil. It is also seen that relatively light coloured oils can be treated effectively to effect substantial reduction in colour by the activated Neyveli clay.

Further experiments on the treatment of alkali-refined vegetable oils with the adsorbents described here are in progress.

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R E F E R E N C E S

1. Unpublished data (work in this laboratory).
2. Joshi & Saletore, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12B p. 381.
3. C. L. Mantell, "Adsorption," McGraw-Hill Book Co., New York and London, p. 320, 1945.
4. *Ibid.* p. 319.
5. Bailey, "Industrial Oil and Fat Products", Interscience Publishers, p. 659, 1951.